

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

Summary of blueprint design for pioneering CCUS chains

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About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

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Abstract
<p>Large scale deployment of CO₂ capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) requires the rolling-out of extensive value chains. In this deliverable, we present the development, design, and techno-economic and environmental analysis of four pioneering chains that include CO₂ capture and conditioning from four existing inland European industrial plants and multi-modal transport to selected ports in Northern Europe. Furthermore, the impact that the implementation of a CCUS chain has on actors along the value chain itself but also along the supply chain of required materials and resources has been evaluated through a social life cycle assessment. Finally, a brief overview of the legal and regulatory framework essential for the effective large-scale deployment of CCUS is provided.</p>

The pioneering chains can avoid between 65% and 87% of the industrial emissions (scope 3 considered), with a cost of CO₂ avoided ranging between ca. 100 and ca. 300 EUR/tCO₂. The geographic location of the industrial emitters proved to be a major factor affecting the economic and environmental performance of the CCUS chains. The analysis relies on the assumption that the four industrial plants would be early-movers. While, in the future, technology maturation and infrastructure development are expected to reduce costs and emissions associated with the CCUS chain, this study quantifies and presents the current economic burden that must be overcome to initiate a needed widespread implementation of CCUS. Therefore, we refer to these four examples as “blueprint designs”, as these chains will serve as models and provide guidance for the development of more advanced CCUS chains.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Document Purpose

The goal of this deliverable is to draw feasible blueprints for the four Pioneering CCUS chains, based on the outcome of Tasks 1 to 3 and looking at all aspects (technology, regulations, impacts, acceptance, costs) considered in those tasks. Therefore, this deliverable assesses all the barriers and gaps still existing for the four Pioneering chains from a holistic perspective, and in view of early implementation. We refer to these four examples as “blueprint designs”, as these chains will serve as models and provide guidance for the development of more advanced CCUS chains. Thus concluding, this deliverable provides the key-messages of WP9, which will be used within the project and for outreach, playing a crucial role in fostering a broad and early implementation of CCUS.

1.2 Relation to other deliverables

These results will feed into the financial and strategical assessment carried out in WP10. Furthermore, they will be the basis for the study of the innovative CCUS chains and their opportunities and challenges, addressed in WP10, as well as in other projects. More specifically, the analysis presented here serves as a basis for deliverable D10.6 Prospective WtE, Cement, pulp and paper, and biorefinery CCUS chains in Europe by 2025-2030. Furthermore, additional details on the CCUS chains analyzed here, on the design basis, and on the methodology used for techno-economic and environmental assessments are reported in the document *Framework for CO₂ capture integration and design and evaluation of CCUS chains*, which has been delivered in February 2022 will be made public via Zenodo at the end of the project.

2 BACKGROUND AND PREVIOUS WORK

The imperative to address climate change and to take measures against the rising levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) has become increasingly urgent. Carbon dioxide capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) has been identified as a key component of climate strategies to mitigate emissions. CCUS offers a promising avenue for capturing CO₂ emissions from large point- source emitters, preventing them from entering the atmosphere, and storing them safely and permanently underground. However, deploying CCUS across Europe is a complex endeavor, with multifaceted technical, economic, and environmental challenges that require careful analysis.

Nonetheless, emitters, especially those located in central Europe, will face the hurdle of having to transport large amounts of CO₂ (on average 250 ktCO₂/y per emitting plant [1]) to a European port. Pipelines have been identified as the most cost-effective CO₂ transport mode onshore for volumes larger than 2 MtCO₂/y for any distance [2]. It is evident that pipelines will be essential for the transport of substantial CO₂ volumes required to meet European countries' climate objectives, which is corroborated by the substantial literature studying the design of CCUS supply chains and networks with focus on ship and pipeline transport [3- 12] [13, 14]. However, the protracted process of planning and constructing this cross-border infrastructure poses a significant challenge - particularly planning has only just started as of now. Moreover, this construction is likely to be a phased process, with initial implementation centered around major industrial clusters in proximity to storage facilities and northern ports. The first pipeline segments might not extend so far to reach larger emission sources that are eager to implement CCUS as early movers. Such pioneers are already looking today for CO₂ capture and transport solutions that can be implemented in the near term. Although the range of CO₂ capture and transport technologies available today is limited, there exist off-the-shelf solutions that can be deployed [15]. This contribution focuses precisely on the design of CCUS value chains relying on readily available CO₂ capture and transport technologies. We consider four large-scale emitters, which are willing to become early CCUS movers, are situated in diverse European locations, and belong to hard-to- abate sectors, i.e., waste treatment, pulp-and-paper production, and cement manufacturing [16]. For each emitter, we design CCUS chains to capture and transport CO₂ from the source to a delivery harbor, from which it will be collected by a storage operator. The chains are analyzed based on their techno-economic and environmental performance. Our ultimate objective is to outline comprehensive guidelines for the integration of CCUS by early movers, with a specific focus on the identification of disadvantages and strategies for easing the burdens encountered by these early movers.

3 PIONEERING CCUS CHAINS

In this study, four pioneering chains are developed, designed, and evaluated (see Fig. 5). The chains are termed "pioneering" as they consider the selected CO₂ emitters as early movers and the CCUS chains as first-of-a-kind. The CO₂ point-source emitters correspond to four existing industrial plants currently advocating the deployment of CCUS as an urgently needed tool to curb their emissions:

- cement plant from Heidelberg Materials (HM) in Hannover, Germany
- a cement plant from Heidelberg Materials (HM) in Góraźdźe, Poland
- a waste-to-energy (WtE) plant from KVA Linth, in Niederurnen, Switzerland
- a pulp mill from Stora Enso (SE) in Skutskär, Sweden.

These emitters cover a wide spectrum of relevant conditions for the deployment of CCUS at an industrial scale. They exhibit different flue gas characteristics, in terms of volume and composition. They present case-specific challenges that are representative of several industrial applications, e.g., availability of energy. Finally, the geographical locations introduce sets of different challenges for the transport of the captured CO₂ to the selected delivery harbor. All in all, the four industries offer a meaningful picture to understand what it takes for the near-term roll-out of CCUS chains from industrial emitters in Europe. In addition, the different degree of utilisation of bio-resources by the four industries allows to investigate existing opportunities to deliver carbon dioxide removal (CDR).

There are several planned and emerging permanent CO₂ storage projects. For the pioneering chains, Northern Lights in Norway will be considered, as it is currently the only open infrastructure storage project under construction with sufficient capacity and with clear expansion plans [17]. The development of the pioneering chains will, therefore, design multi-modal transport to convey CO₂ to a selected port in Northern Europe. From the port, it is assumed that CO₂ is transported directly via ship to the Northern Lights receiving terminal, but the cost and emissions related to this final step are not accounted for in this study. It is important to be aware of such boundaries when analysing the results. For instance, whenever an emission reduction figure or a cost is reported, these refer to the amount of CO₂ avoided by capturing, conditioning, and transporting CO₂ from the industrial site to the selected port. The transport via ship to the Northern Lights receiving terminal or to other offshore storage sites will result in additional emissions, and increased costs. Nonetheless, the decision to focus on the delivery harbor as the final point for the analysis in this study offers a strategic advantage that extends beyond the immediate context of the Northern Lights storage site. By choosing the harbor as the end point, we ensure that the results obtained can be extrapolated and applied to other storage hubs accessible from the same harbors and currently under development [18, 19, 20, 21].

The flue gas (stream 1) is pre-cooled in a direct contact cooler (DCC) before entering the absorber where the CO₂ is absorbed. A water wash section tops the column to recover solvent from the exhaust gases. In the case of the two cement plants and of the pulp and paper plant, a second water-wash section is needed to remain within the desired amine emission limits. The CO₂ depleted gas (stream 5) is released to the atmosphere. Depending on the flue gas temperature a gas-gas heat exchanger is included to achieve a wide spread of the vapour plume [26]. It is considered for the plants in Hannover, Góraźdźe and Skutskär, conversely it is not considered for the plant in Niederurnen. The CO₂ rich solvent (stream 7) is sent to the stripper. Regeneration of the solvent is achieved by heating with steam in a reboiler. The purified CO₂ leaves from the top of the stripper (stream 16). The lean solvent (stream 10) is circulated back to the absorber. A thermal reclaimer is included to purify the solvent and allows for spent solvent disposition. A lean-rich heat exchanger is used for energy recovery. The capture process for the different cases considered here has been simulated using Aspen Plus V10.

Steam is normally used for regenerating the CO₂-rich solvent. The following options for using biofuels for steam production have been considered: (1) biogas for the cases of cement and WtE plants, and (2) biomass for the case of the pulp mill.

The CO₂ captured needs to be compressed and/or liquefied to the desired conditions depending on the transport solutions. In this study, liquefaction at a pressure of 15 barg is considered. A schematic of the CO₂ liquefaction process is shown in Figure 2, while more information on the cycle selected can be found in Deng et al. [27]. The process has been studied using rigorous mass and energy balance models developed with Aspen HYSYS V10 for all the relevant process units using property packages and parameters reported by Deng et al. [27]. The SQP-based optimization utility within HYSYS has been used to minimize the overall specific energy consumption of the system considering the following decision variables: (1) the pressure ratios of the various compressor stages, (2) the valve outlet pressures, and (3) the cooler outlet temperatures.

Figure 2. Process flowsheet of the CO₂ liquefaction unit. Adapted from [27].

4.2 CO₂ transport

As this study focuses on pioneering chains, we consider CO₂ transport options that can be implemented in the near term, i.e., mature technologies that do not require any considerable greenfield infrastructure outside of the emitter's site or of the receiving harbor. This implies that large intermediate storage facilities and filling stations at exchange sites, the construction of new railway stations and the construction or refurbishment of pipelines, as well as technologies under development such as dedicated barges and ships are outside the scope of this study. All transport options considered in this study carry CO₂ in the liquid state at medium pressure (15 barg and -27 °C at loading). CO₂ can be loaded into ISO tank containers (typically referred to as isotainers), each holding approximately 20 tCO₂. These isotainers have the same dimensions as typical freight containers and can be loaded onto trucks, trains, barges (on rivers), and ships (on open waters). The CO₂ remains in the container throughout the whole supply chain, and the isotainers are exchanged between transport modes by means of a crane. An alternative option consists of relying on fixed tanks to be installed on dedicated trucks and trains, which generally have a larger capacity than isotainers. More details about the different transport options can be found in Oeuvray et al. [2].

The topology and existing infrastructure at each emitter site are decisive concerning the potential deployment of specific transport solutions. The cement plant in Hannover has a private railway station and can also accommodate transport by truck. However, despite being connected to the Stichkanal Misburg, which is a branch of the Mittellandkanal, there is currently no operation of cargo barge from there, and dedicated barge transport is not considered in this study. The situation is similar for the cement plant in Góraždze, which has a private railway station too, but no water connection because the Oder River flowing nearby is not navigable for large vessels. The WtE plant KVA Linth is far from any navigable river and railway transport is not a viable option (the plant has no private railway station, while the closest freight railway stations do not give permission to transship CO₂). There is

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nonetheless road access, and the plant is located close to the highway. The pulp mill in Skutskär is situated directly by the sea and has a private harbor; therefore, there is no need for transport from the emitter to the harbor.

4.3 Methodology for cost assessment

4.3.1 Capture and conditioning

The four chains are analyzed in a consistent manner, whereby the economic assessment includes estimations of investment costs, as well as of fixed and variable operation and maintenance costs of the different elements of the chain. An important aspect of the analysis is that the evaluated chains are FOAK (First-of-a-kind) or near-FOAK, i.e., early movers and in the early stages of commercialization, which translates into higher implementation costs with respect to n^{th} -of-a-kind plants. In this study, the FOAK cost evaluations are performed following the guidelines described by Roussanaly et al. [28, 29].

Economic evaluations are calculated on an EBIDTA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation, and Amortization) basis and reported for 2020, with an economic lifetime of 20 years and a discount rate of 10%. Both investment and operational costs are higher for FOAK projects compared to mature plant costs. Among others, some typical reasons for higher investment costs are sub-optimal and oversized design and stricter design standards, additional spare and redundant equipment, higher process and system contingencies, delays in construction, and higher discount rate to reflect risk premium.

The system contingency factor (10%) reflects additional capital costs related to the integration of the CO₂ capture and conditioning process within the industrial plant and is unique to initial installations of a new technology. The total capital requirement is estimated using a bottom-up approach, in which equipment costs are obtained from Aspen Process Economic Analyzer. Figure 3 shows the steps and the factors to estimate the total capital requirement. Interest over construction is estimated considering that construction costs are shared over a 3.5-year construction period, following a 20%/30%/30%/20% allocation for each year.

Figure 3 Bottom-up approach for the estimation of the total capital requirement.

Additional operating costs can also be expected in the first years of operation, especially for a demonstration project due to e.g., learning and training time and inefficiency. Operating costs consider reduced capacity factors for the first two years of operation, i.e., 40% and 65%, and increased maintenance and labor costs. Utility consumption is therefore assumed to be 15% higher than the basis during the first three years of operation [30]. The costs of utilities are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 Costs of utilities used for the techno-economic analysis.

Utility	Unit	Value
Process water [31]	€/m ³	6.65
Cooling water	€/m ³	0.039
AMP solvent [32]	€ ₂₀₁₅ /kg	8
PZ solvent [32]	€ ₂₀₁₅ /kg	6
Solvent sludge disposal [33]	€ ₂₀₁₅ /t	205
Molecular sieve [34]	€/t	3600
Steam from biomass	€/GJ	18.2
Steam from biogas	€/GJ	13.9

Electricity costs differ significantly depending on the location. For the plants in Germany, Poland and Sweden, electricity costs given by Eurostat [35] are used. For the plant located in Switzerland, information is retrieved from the Swiss Federal Electricity Commission [36]. Table 2 shows the electricity costs used for the techno-economic analysis.

Table 2 Electricity costs for the CO₂ capture and conditioning plants [35, 36].

Plant	Country	Unit	Value
HM Hannover	Germany	€/kWh	0.1065
HM Góraźdże	Poland	€/kWh	0.0775
SE Skutskär	Sweden	€/kWh	0.0455
KVA Linth	Switzerland	CHF/kWh	0.0758

4.3.2 Transport

The assessment of the transport costs is based on the methodology described by Oeuvray et al. [2]. The techno-economic assessment considers capital and operational expenditures derived from the transport distance and duration; they include infrastructure, rolling material, labor, maintenance, fuel, insurances and taxes, administrative fees, and supplements.

The data has been collected directly from selected industrial and logistics companies, whenever possible. Based on the identified transport exchange terminals and the feasible connections, a network outlining feasible paths leading to a specific harbor is generated for each emitter. This network can be visualized as a directed graph, whereby the nodes represent transport exchange sites where a transport mode exchange can occur, and the edges represent direct connections between two nodes. The weight of each edge is determined by the transportation cost associated with the available transport option for that connection. The Yen's algorithm [37] is used on the simple directed graph to determine the cost-effective routes from a source to a specified harbor.

4.3.3 Cost of CO₂ avoided

The economic performance of the pioneering chains is mainly assessed through the cost of CO₂ avoided (CAC). The CAC measures the cost to avoid a unit of CO₂ emissions. The CAC is defined as the ratio between the net present value of CCS implementation cost (including capital and operational expenditures) and the discounted amount of CO₂ emissions avoided throughout the years [38]:

$$CAC = \frac{NPV_{CCS}}{\sum_i \frac{m_{CO_2,avoided,i}}{(1+r)^i}} \quad (1)$$

with NPV_{CCS} being the net present value of total annual CCS costs (which may vary from year to year), $m_{CO_2,avoided,i}$ the mass of CO₂ avoided by CCS implementation in year i and r the discount rate.

4.4 Methodology for Life Cycle Assessment

4.4.1 Environmental Life Cycle Assessment

The life cycle assessment (LCA) quantifies the climate change and other environmental impacts of the four pioneering CCUS chains from the CO₂ capture up to the delivery of the CO₂ to the nearest harbor. The LCA's system boundary includes all emissions of the CCUS chains, while excluding the point source itself (cf. Figure 4).

The processes in the system boundaries are grouped into three sub-systems: Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 emissions, following the definitions of the greenhouse gas (GHG) protocol [39]. Scope 3 emissions include all other indirect emissions from up- and downstream processes. Upstream processes can be the production of steel and concrete for construction while downstream emissions occur, for example, in the treatment of waste streams. [40]

Figure 4: System boundary of the LCA divided into Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 emissions. Scope 2 emissions include the whole life-cycle of the electricity generation.

The LCA is based on the ACCESS deliverable D9.3 and the work of Burger et al. [41] and follows the methodology defined in ISO 14040:2021 and ISO 14044:2021 [42, 43]. The global warming impact (GWI) of the pioneering chains is assessed using the global warming potential over a 100-year time horizon from the “Environmental Footprint” version 3.0 impact assessment methods [44]. All impacts are scaled on a functional unit, which is the product or service delivered by the corresponding point source. Therefore, the functional unit is one ton of clinker ($t_{clinker}$) for both cement plants, one ton of incinerated municipal solid waste (t_{waste}) for the WtE plant, and one air-dried ton of pulp (adt_{pulp}) for the pulp mill.

By quantifying the chain's GHG emissions, the LCA shows the potential for (1) the amount of avoided CO₂ and (2) the amount of CDR to be generated:

$$m_{\text{CO}_2, \text{avoided}} = m_{\text{CO}_2, \text{captured}} - \text{CC}_{\text{chain}} \quad (2)$$

with $m_{\text{CO}_2, \text{avoided}}$ being the avoided CO₂ emissions potential, CC_{chain} the climate change impact of the chain, and $m_{\text{CO}_2, \text{captured}}$ the amount of CO₂ captured. The avoided emissions potential, together with the share of the total CO₂ emissions ($m_{\text{CO}_2, \text{total}}$) which is of biogenic origin (β), determines the CDR potential of the CCUS chains:

$$m_{\text{CO}_2, \text{CDR}} = (1 - \beta) m_{\text{CO}_2, \text{total}} - m_{\text{CO}_2, \text{avoided}} \quad (3)$$

Thus, if the process emits less biogenic CO₂ than the CCUS chain can avoid, there is no potential for CDR. However, to reliably quantify CDR, not only the potential, the criteria from Tanzer and Ramírez [45] should be used. As the system boundary ends at the nearest harbor (cf. Figure 4) it excludes maritime transport to the storage site and the subsequent geological storage. Both steps cause GHG emissions that must be included to quantify the overall avoided CO₂ from the point source. Consequently, the presented LCA quantifies the potential of the CCUS chains for CO₂ avoidance and for delivering CDR with respect to capture and inland transport, which have the largest environmental impact. In fact, an LCA of the maritime CO₂ transport and offshore storage at the Northern Lights storage site estimates life cycle emissions of 2.6 % with respect to the total amount of CO₂ injected [46]. Therefore, the influence of these steps of the CCUS chain on the overall CO₂ avoidance potential is limited.

While the goal of CCUS chains is the reduction of GWI of the industrial point source, CCUS chains unavoidably lead to other environmental impacts. Thus, we analyze fifteen additional environmental impact categories besides GWI to quantify the extent of burden-shifting.

4.4.2 Social Life Cycle Assessment

The value chain installed for the permanent storage of CO₂ not only causes environmental impacts but also affects human beings and society: Human beings are involved in building and operating the value chain and are passively affected by both construction and operation. From the point source to the storage site, several groups of actors may be affected. A social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) has been conducted to evaluate the impact that the implementation of a CCUS chain has on actors along the value chain itself but also along the supply chain of required materials and resources.

Compared to conventional LCAs, S-LCAs can emphasize positive impacts and thus influence political decisions [47]. Notably, these positive effects stem from the value chain, not the product itself. S-LCAs, as per UNEP guidelines [48], exclude health impacts stemming from environmental aspects as these are better investigated with conventional LCAs. The research on S-LCA varies between quantitative and qualitative approaches [49]. Our S-LCA, aligned with UNEP guidelines, aims to establish a benchmark for future studies on point source CCTS. The data-driven approach identifies social hot spots for subsequent qualitative studies and comparisons between CO₂ supply chains. The scope definition clarifies the conditions for the S-LCA's validity. The S-LCA uses 1 ton of CO₂ delivered to a harbor at the North Sea as a functional unit. The capture, conditioning, and transport steps are included in the system boundary, aligning with the conventional LCA (cf. Figure 4).

In S-LCA, selecting the considered stakeholder groups, subcategories, and indicators significantly shapes the assessment of social aspects. As per UNEP guidelines [48], key stakeholders include *Workers, Local communities, Value chain actors, Consumers, Children, and Society*. However, customization is possible based on focus or data availability. This S-LCA utilizes the PSILCA commercial database [50], containing 55 predefined indicators across 22 subcategories and four stakeholder groups. Of these, 44 indicators are chosen for analysis, excluding environmental aspects, as conventional LCAs address them more comprehensively. Although *Consumers* and *Children* are not explicitly listed, they are implicitly covered by other stakeholder groups. For example, *Children* are assessed through the *Workers* and *Society* stakeholder groups, considering indicators like 'Child labour' and 'Youth illiteracy.' For the background processes, we use the database PSILCA to determine social impact indicators. The database contains information for over 14 000 industries for 189 countries and thus covers a wide range of processes. All impacts from the industries are allocated based on the amount of money flowing into a particular industry. However, the density of industries varies greatly between countries, and the nomenclature is not entirely consistent. Therefore, the compilation of life cycle inventories has some limitations and is not as rigorous as for a conventional LCA.

The PSILCA database utilizes 'worker hours' to generate the risk impacts. Initially, the average time required to generate one USD output is calculated for each industry. The resulting 'worker hours' per USD exhibit significant variation globally [50]. Subsequently, PSILCA assigns risk levels (no risk, very low risk, low risk, medium risk, high risk, very high risk) to each indicator within each industry, with clearly defined levels found in [50]. The risk levels are multiplied with the working hours to obtain 'med risk hours.' For example, if 0.2 hours are required in the 'Construction' industry in Switzerland to generate one USD output and there is a high risk associated with the 'safety measures' indicator (risk factor of 10), the impact is calculated as 2 'med risk hours,' which is then aggregated along the value chain.

PSILCA estimates the social impact of each USD spent, making cost estimates crucial. In this S-LCA, cost estimation relies on the cost optimization from WP9. To calculate the social impact, the costs of value chains are distributed among various industries. Initially, the cost of each value chain part is divided into construction and use phases (CAPEX and OPEX, respectively). The costs of CAPEX for CO₂ processing steps and OPEX for carbon capture are allocated, as outlined in Table 3.

Table 3: Cost contribution of CAPEX and OPEX derived from IEAGHG [51]

	Expense account	Cost share
CAPEX	Purchased Equipment	23%
	Purchased Equipment Delivery	2%
	Piping	17%
	Electrical Equipment and Materials	5%
	Engineering and Supervision	8%
	Construction	45%
OPEX	Consumables	56%
	Insurance	6%
	Taxes	6%
	O&M	31%

5 RESULTS

Figure 5: Illustration of the four pioneering chains.

The pioneering transport chains selected are shown on a map of Central/Northern Europe in Figure 5. In detail, the cement plant in Hannover, Germany, is connected with the harbour of Wilhelmshaven by dedicated road transport. Trucks effectuate daily roundtrips on the 235 km-long connection to transport the captured CO₂ from the cement plant to the harbour. The cement plant in Górażdże, Poland, is connected via railway to the harbour of Szczecin, located 450 km apart. Five trains composed of dedicated wagons convey the CO₂ daily. The total distance travelled is longer for the CO₂ captured at the WtE plant in Niederurnen, which is located in Switzerland, a land-locked country. In this case, the CO₂ is loaded into isotainers, which are transported by truck to Basel and by barge thereafter, over the 1000 km from Niederurnen to the harbour of Rotterdam. Finally, due to its coastal location and its infrastructure, the pulp mill in Skutskär, Sweden, has a direct access to a suitable port.

Table 4: CO₂ emissions and avoidance values for the pioneering chains. In the table CCR stands for CO₂ capture rate (higher than 89% in all cases as a result of a 90% CO₂ captured from the capture unit and of a minor CO₂ loss in the conditioning unit).

		Biogenic CO ₂ uptake $U_{\text{bio, input}}$	Total CO ₂ emissions (biogenic/fossil) $E_{\text{tot, input}}$	CO ₂ captured $C_{\text{CO}_2} = E_{\text{tot}} \cdot \text{CCR}$	Direct & indirect emissions $E_{\text{d/i, input}}$	CO ₂ avoided (reduction/removal) $E_{\text{avo}} = C_{\text{CO}_2} - E_{\text{d/i}}$
Hannover	kg _{CO₂} /t _{clinker}	52	868 (52/816)	777	129	648 (648/0)
Górażdże	kg _{CO₂} /t _{clinker}	97	884 (97/786)	790	221	570 (570/0)
Niederurnen	kg _{CO₂} /t _{waste}	645	1241 (645/596)	1113	188	925 (596/330)
Skutskär	kg _{CO₂} /adt _{pulp}	2041	2041 (2041/0)	1837	57	1780 (0/1780)

Figure 6: CO₂ emissions accounting for the pioneering chains.

Figure 6 shows the complete CO₂ emissions accounting for the four pioneering chains in terms of specific CO₂ emissions – defined as the amount of direct and indirect CO₂ emissions per unit of industrial product. Table 3 reports the related emissions and avoidance values. Without CCS, each plant is responsible for an amount of CO₂ emissions depending on the industrial process (burgundy bar). Whenever bio-feedstocks are used, that results in the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere (blue bar). The CO₂ uptake further establishes the biogenic fraction of the total emissions (the part of the burgundy bar below the zero of the vertical axis), and consequently the fossil fraction (the part of the burgundy bar above the zero). For example, the biogenic CO₂ fraction of the emissions from the Hannover cement plant corresponds to 6% (52 of the total 816 kgCO₂/t clinker), while for the Skutskär pulp mill the fraction is 100%. The implementation of CCS implies that a large amount of the industrial CO₂ emissions is captured and conditioned at site to be made ready for transport (grey bar). The share of CO₂ emissions that is captured is defined by the CO₂ capture rate (CCR). The CCR corresponds to 90% for all the capture plants, a value that is slightly reduced due to CO₂ losses in the conditioning process (the actual CCR is above 89% for all chains). Upon implementation of the CO₂ supply chain, direct and indirect emissions (scope 1, 2, and 3) occur and must be accounted for (stacked bars – each scope is represented with a different colour, i.e., orange, red, brown). These additional emissions reduce the potential for CO₂ avoidance (reduction and/or removal).

The quantity called CO₂ avoided can be obtained as the difference between the total CO₂ emitted to the atmosphere without CCS and the CO₂ emitted after implementation of the CCS scheme; the latter stems either at the plant because the CO₂ capture rate is less than 100%, or directly and indirectly along the CO₂ chain. The CO₂ avoided term comprises of both CO₂ emissions reduced (green bar, solid) and CO₂ emissions removed (green bar, dashed). The relative share depends on the fossil and biogenic content, respectively, of the total CO₂ emissions, in accordance with the principles outlined in Section 4.4. The CO₂ reduction expresses the decrease of net CO₂ emissions (the biogenic CO₂ is not accounted for in this case as its emission closes a material cycle and results in no net increase in CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere) released into the atmosphere with respect to the plant without CCS. The CO₂ removal implies that there is also a net removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere due to the implementation of CCS, thus resulting in CDR amounts. The WtE plant and the pulp mill make large use of bio-resources in their industrial processes, yielding a significant uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere. The corresponding large fraction of biogenic emissions leads to CO₂ removal. Conversely, the cement plants, at today's conditions, although reaching significant CO₂ reduction figures, do not achieve CO₂ removal.

Based on the emissions accounting described, the pioneering chains exhibit a potential to avoid 65% to 87% of their emissions. The residual emissions are due to the capture process mostly (i.e., the CCR is lower than 100%). Another relevant contribution is associated with the energy needed to implement the CCUS chain, which causes direct (scope 1) and indirect (scope 2) CO₂ emissions. As explained in Section 3, it is important to bear in mind that the results presented here reflect the pioneering CCUS chains from capture until the delivery harbor, excluding offshore transport and storage at Northern Lights.

Figure 7: Breakdown into chain elements of the specific energy consumption for the pioneering chains. The following figures were obtained: 3473 MJ/t_{clinker} and 3477 MJ/t_{clinker} for the cement plants in Hannover and Górażdże; 5568 MJ/t_{waste} for the WtE plant; and 7938 MJ/adt_{pulp} for the pulp mill.

The main energy inputs are power and heat for the capture and conditioning processes, as well as fuels (i.e., trucks and barges) or electricity (i.e. trains) for the means of transportation. The relative breakdown of the specific primary energy consumption into the chain elements is presented in Figure 7, while the absolute numbers are reported in the caption. The capture process is by far the main contributor to the energy consumption for all the chains. Energy-wise, transport plays a significant role for the chains located far from a harbour (e.g., the Niederurnen chain).

Figure 8: Breakdown into chain elements of the specific CO₂ emissions of the pioneering chains.

The breakdown into chain elements of the specific CO₂ emissions is presented in Figure 8. Although the energy requirements for capture are dominant, its impact on the environmental performance is more limited. This is related to the utilization of biofuels such as biogas and biomass to produce steam for the capture process. Conversely, despite having a smaller energy requirement, power-driven processes, such as CO₂ liquefaction, may have a significant carbon footprint depending on the carbon intensity of the electricity mix. That is, for instance, the case of the two cement plants chains, which source electricity from national grid mixes that still rely heavily on fossil fuels. Overall, the most impactful factors on the emissions results are: (1) the different types of fuels used and their associated CO₂ intensity, (2) the CO₂ factor of the electrical grid mix, and (3) the length of the transport route from source to harbour, whereby the geographic location of the emitting industrial plants affects significantly the last two factors. The large impact of geographic location is also revealed by the analysis of the economic performance of the pioneering chains.

Figure 9: Breakdown into (1) chain elements and (2) cost terms of the cost of CO₂ avoided of the pioneering chains.

Figure 9 shows both the breakdown of the CAC with respect to chain elements and cost contributions. The capture plant is on average the dominant factor. Similarly to the energy and emissions figures, the cost of transport becomes relevant in certain cases (e.g., the WtE chain) depending on the location of the industrial plant. A long distance to the nearest port requires the design of a complex, extensive, and expensive transport route. Vice versa the proximity to a port obviously allows to reduce the cost of CO₂ transport. In addition, an industrial site located in a

favourable position, such as along a navigable river, results again in lower transport costs. The geographical location has also an effect on the cost of the energy sources (primarily the cost of electricity) and on their carbon footprint. An example of a pioneering chain benefiting from a favourable geographic location is the pulp mill chain. The pulp mill is located on the coast (indeed no transport costs are included) and in a country (i.e., Sweden) characterized by relatively inexpensive and clean electricity. A different example is offered by the WtE plant in Switzerland: it can make use of relatively clean electricity locally, but it faces major energy and cost burdens, because of the need to transport the CO₂ to the port of Rotterdam, i.e., through a fairly long transport route, along which fossil fuels play still a major role.

Other factors that have a significant impact on the costs are the scale and the characteristics of the industrial flue gas to treat. Larger scales lead to smaller specific costs of the capture and conditioning units, at least with the technologies considered. For instance, this contributes to a cost gap of ca. 60 €/tCO₂ for capture and conditioning between the largest industrial installation (i.e., the Góraźdże cement plant) and the smallest one (i.e., the WtE plant). Potentially, the characteristics of the flue gas can have an impact too, especially in terms of CO₂ concentration. However, the range of concentrations of the four industrial flue gases considered, i.e., between 12% and 20% in volume, yields differences in cost of capture, which are possibly below the intrinsic uncertainty we have in determining the costs of the entire chain [52].

Concerning the contribution of various cost terms, the OPEX is normally the major component, when all its terms are summed together. Among those, the variable OPEX related to steam production (i.e., OPEX Steam) and the variable OPEX "others" (a term that includes non-energy related costs such as the cost of chemicals and the costs incurred in operating the transport logistics) are the two largest costs, although the latter, being mainly related to transport, is more case-specific. CAPEX is consistently a relevant share of the overall CAC, irrespective of the industrial case.

Figure 10: Cost of CO₂ avoided, CAC, of the pioneering chains and effect of different boundaries of the direct and indirect emissions considered.

All the factors described concur to determine the CAC of the pioneering chains. The CAC achieved is shown in Figure 10, including the effect of different boundaries of indirect emissions considered (i.e., scope 1, 2 and 3). The pioneering chains exhibit a CAC between ca. 100 and ca. 300 €/tCO₂.

The figure shows the impact of different boundaries to the emissions accounting: capture cost includes only non-captured emissions (grey bars), while the increase of cost related to direct and indirect emissions (scope 1, 2 and 3) along the chain are added on top (brown, red and orange bars, respectively). The effect of the additional emissions may be significant – e.g., the final cost figure is increased by 40% in the case of Górażdże. The impact of designing a complex value chain can also be noted, for instance, by comparing the results for Niederurnen and Skutskär. The need for long transport routes, as is the case for industrial emitters located in inland Europe, implies costs for operating the transport logistics (a key factor explaining the difference between the grey bars), and direct and indirect emissions along the chain (particularly scope 1 and 2 emissions, in brown and red in the figure). Increased costs and emissions lead to higher CAC values.

While the goal of CCUS chains is the reduction of GWI of the industrial point sources, they unavoidably lead to other environmental impacts. Thus, we analyze 15 additional environmental impact categories besides GWI to quantify the extent of burden-shifting. For this purpose, we use the Environmental Footprint methods, version 3.0, to quantify the environmental impacts [44]. The environmental impacts for all pioneering chains shown in Figure 11 include direct and indirect emissions (i.e., scope 1, 2 and 3).

Figure 11: LCA results for all pioneering chains including direct and indirect emissions (i.e., scope 1, 2 and 3) and normalization of the impacts of the chain from Niederurnen. Thus, the Niederurnen chain has a value of 1 in each impact category. Note that "Eutrophication: Freshwater" and "Land use: Soil quality index" extend over the axis limits.

In contrast to the functional units defined in Chapter 4.4, the environmental impacts are determined for 1 ton of CO₂ captured, conditioned and transported to the nearest harbour. Furthermore, each environmental impact is normalized to the corresponding impact of the chain from Niederurnen to enable a comparison between the four pioneering chains.

The Niederurnen chain has the highest environmental impact in 6 out of 16 categories, while it only achieves the lowest impact in one category. The impact categories where the Niederurnen

chain achieves the highest impact are dominated by the transportation step, accounting for more than 50% of the total impact in the respective categories. The high share in impacts of the transportation step result from the distance between Niederurnen and the harbour in Rotterdam, which is more than twice as large as the distance for the other pioneering chains.

The HC Góraźdze chain has the largest environmental impact in 5 out of 16 impact categories. These impact categories are dominated by the utilities for the capture and conditioning step, contributing to more than 50% of the environmental impact. The Polish electricity grid mix is heavily dependent on the combustion of fossil fuels, such as coal, leading to a high environmental impact in many categories. In the category "*Eutrophication: Freshwater*", this is particularly evident with an impact nine times greater than the impact of the Niederurnen chain. In 2 out of 16 impact categories, the Góraźdze chain achieves the smallest environmental impact.

The chain from Skutskär shows the best performance in 7 of the 16 analysed impact categories. The Skutskär chain benefits from the Swedish electricity mix, mainly based on renewable and nuclear power and the fact that no transport step is required due to direct harbour access. However, the Skutskär chain has the largest impact in 4 categories. These impacts are mainly driven by the use of biomass boilers to generate the steam for the capture process and, in the case of the "*Ionising radiation: Human health*" impact category, by the large share of nuclear power in the Swedish electricity grid mix. Thereby, the impact on "*Land use: Soil quality index*" exceeds the impact of the Niederurnen chain by a factor of 4.

The chain from Hannover achieves the best performance in 6 of the 16 impact categories while having the largest impact in only one impact category. However, it should be noted that the "*Eutrophication: Freshwater*" impact is 5 times larger than for the Niederurnen chain. Similar to the Góraźdze chain, the impact can be attributed to the local electricity grid mix.

The S-LCA results are used to compare the risk for negative impacts on stakeholder groups between the pioneering CCUS chains. The chain starting in Góraźdze shows the most risk in 25 out of 44 indicators compared to the other three chains. The chain from Skutskär is on the opposite side of the scale with only 1 indicator, which is higher than the other three chains. Therefore, out of the four analyzed systems, the value chain starting in Góraźdze is, in comparison, most likely to cause negative effects due to the installation and operation of the chain.

An assessment of the absolute risk impact for the value chain starting in Góraźdze shows which indicators have an absolute high risk and require further careful consideration. The medium risk value is set at 1, designating everything below as low risk and above as high risk. Despite the Góraźdze chain being identified as the most risk-prone among the pioneering chains, most indicators are below 1 med risk hour/tCO₂/USD, with only 7 out of 44 indicators surpassing this threshold (cf. Figure 12). High-risk indicators are, e.g., *Trade unionism*, *Promoting social responsibility*, and *Fair salary*, which tend to have more risk for the other chains, too.

In general, the S-LCA showed that among the four assessed chains, the chain going from Góraźdze to Sczechin has the highest risk associated with its installation and operation. However, in absolute terms most indicators show low risk and are therefore considered to have no negative effects along the supply chain. The indicators showing high risk for Góraźdze are also high risk in most of the other chains and, therefore, require careful assessment as to their real risk and the effects that the CCTS chain has on stakeholders along its supply chain. However, the presented analysis is only capable of identifying hotspots and highlighting areas of concern that may then be analyzed in more detail afterward. To capture the full extent of impacts on stakeholders such as workers, society, and local communities, the presented hotspot analysis can be taken as a basis. The identified hotspots could be examined in more detail in collaboration with the actual companies and stakeholders involved to build better knowledge about the effects of the value chain.

Figure 12: Indicators and associated risk values for the value chain from Góraždze in ascending order. The grey box marks all indicators higher than average risk (>1).

6 DISCUSSION AND LEARNINGS

6.1 Cost of full-scale demo capture facilities

A distinctive aspect of the cost evaluations presented in this work is that both investment and operating cost estimations try and consider the uncertainties that early-movers face. As explained in Section 3.3, this is reflected in e.g., larger contingency costs, system contingencies, and increased utility consumption in the first years of operation. With a more widespread deployment of CO₂ capture facilities in different industries and under different scenarios, it is unavoidable that the predictability with respect to technology and technology integration will grow, thus reducing the need for more contingencies, increasing standardization, hence reducing investment costs. Moreover, the accumulation of practical know-how will also translate into more efficient operation and lower operating costs. With this accumulated experience, *Nth*-of-a-kind (NOAK) CO₂ capture and conditioning plants, are expected to have lower investment and operating costs than those estimated in this work.

For absorption-based CO₂ capture, the cost of steam for solvent regeneration is a major contributor to the overall costs, as demonstrated in Fig. 9 for the four evaluated cases, where also investment and other operating costs have been considered. In this evaluation, steam is produced in dedicated biogas or biomass boilers, thus resulting in a large cost penalty. However, the industrial deployment must target the minimization of the loss of electricity generation (e.g., in the WtE plant) and of the investment and operation cost of a new boiler. The recovery of surplus heat from the industrial process to produce steam must be considered, though it may be more or less challenging for different industries or for specific plants, depending e.g., on the available temperature levels, on the existing degree of heat integration, or on temporary and seasonal variations [53, 54, 55, 56].

Economies of scale have been highlighted as a key element to reduce the cost of a full-scale CCS infrastructure (e.g., [57, 58]). The results in Fig. 9 confirm this trend, with lower specific capture costs (in EUR/tCO_{2,avoided}) for the larger units, i.e., the cement plants and the pulp mill, compared to the higher CO₂ capture costs for the much smaller WtE plant. It is worth remembering that the chains evaluated in this contribution consider single point-source emitters. As CCUS chains roll out, there will be the option of establishing capture hubs, especially around already existing industrial hubs, which typically include cement and waste management facilities [59, 60]. This will result not only in the possibility of having shared utility and surplus heat utilization networks, but also CO₂ capture clusters for multiple emitting streams, with shared capture, conditioning and intermediate storage facilities. This may enable cost reductions, especially for smaller emitters close to larger ones [61, 62].

6.2 Cost of transport for early movers located in inland Europe

The costs of transport associated with the supply chains of the emitters considered in this study are shown in Fig. 9. The associated transport pathways can differ in cost, velocity, required logistics, and operational-to-capital expenditures ratio. It is worth noting that the costs of transport reflect mainly the distance, because the existing transport options are modular and thus offer limited economies of scale. The transport costs are predominantly attributable to operating expenditures for all transport pathways in this study; however, the allocation between capital and operational expenditures primarily depends on the selected transport options, which involve either the acquisition or the rental of the equipment. Even though it may merely be anecdotal, the following observation suggests a general guideline for inland transportation costs with pioneering

transport options: the cost from emitter to harbor scales linearly with distance, with a unitary cost of ca. 1 EUR/tCO₂ transported over 10 km.

6.3 Supporting the burden of early movers and valuing CDR

As highlighted in the earlier sections, the CO₂ avoidance cost from capture to harbour of the four considered CCUS chains varies between ca. 100 and ca. 300 EUR/tCO_{2,avoided}. The costs of the CO₂ transport from harbour to storage hub and of the storage itself will likely add at least, several tens of EUR/tCO_{2,avoided}. These costs are significantly higher than the current CO₂ emissions price under the European Union's Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) [63], thus making CCUS deployment from the facilities under the EU ETS not economically viable today.

A significant challenge for the four CCUS chains analyzed here is the higher costs incurred as early movers, which might result in the decision to delay implementation. To overcome this key challenge to implementation, several possibilities could be explored [64].

Support to partly cover the burden of the investment costs could be sought at the national level or at the European Union level [64]. Such measures include contributions to up-front costs, grants to cover engineering studies, e.g., Front End Engineering Design (FEED), loan support (enabling preferential interest rates, access to debt capital, and loan guarantees), and tax credits. A similar strategy could be seeking operational subsidies at the national or EU level to create predictable revenue streams [64]. This could be achieved through, e.g., tax credits and/or contracts-for-difference.

Another opportunity for some of these CCUS chains is to try and create the largest value from the generated CDR. As highlighted in Fig. 6, two of the chains considered here can generate significant levels of CDR through the capture and permanent storage of biogenic CO₂ produced by these facilities.

Indeed, high-quality CDR in voluntary carbon markets or in private financial agreements are valued at prices as high as 700 \$/tCO₂ [65, 66]. Let us consider the case of the WtE plant located in Niederurnen, Switzerland. Without any revenue from selling the generated CDR, the plant faces a cost of CO₂ avoided for its fossil emissions of ca. 500 EUR/tCO_{2,avoided}. A revenue of ca. 400 EUR/tCDR would roughly half the cost of CO₂ avoided; if such revenue would increase to ca. 800 EUR/tCDR, the cost would be reduced by more than 90%. Finally, in addition to the above points, another possibility is to pass down the additional costs due to the implementation of CCUS to the end-users of the relevant products. Indeed, as highlighted by recent studies [67, 68], a high CO₂ avoidance cost does not necessarily result in a major cost increase for the end-users of the final products derived from these industrial plants; this could be absorbed by the end-users relatively easily if the proper mechanisms were in place.

6.4 International and European Regulatory Framework for CCTS

While CCUS has reached technical readiness for implementation, the legal and regulatory framework essential for its effective large-scale deployment and oversight is still in need of revision and updating.

The International and European regulatory framework is working to enable the implementation and deployment of CCUS technologies through global agreements and national legislation. International law serves as the cornerstone for CCUS activities, emphasizing the importance of

responsible practices and cross-border cooperation. Key international agreements, such as the OSPAR Convention and the London Protocol, are instrumental in shaping the regulatory landscape for CCUS, particularly regarding the protection of the marine environment and permanent CO₂ storage beneath the seabed.

The EU regulatory framework for CCUS revolves around key components, notably the EU ETS and the CO₂ Storage Directive. The integration of CCUS into the EU ETS is crucial, given that this legislation forms the cornerstone for reducing greenhouse gas emissions across various sectors. The CO₂ Storage Directive establishes a comprehensive regulatory framework within the EU, addressing key elements such as cross-border transport of CO₂ for storage, third-party access to CO₂ transport networks, qualitative standards for CO₂ purity, and the issue of long-term liability.

In light of these advancements, it is crucial to recognize that despite the technical readiness of CCUS, legal questions and challenges must be effectively addressed for the large-scale and successful implementation of these technologies [69].

7 CONCLUSIONS

The development, design, and techno-economic and environmental analysis of four pioneering chains is performed. The four industrial sites considered are two cement plants from Heidelberg Materials (Hannover, Germany, and Góraźdze, Poland), a waste-to-energy plant from KVA Linth (Niederurnen, Switzerland) and a pulp mill from Stora Enso (Skutskär, Sweden). The pioneering chains include CO₂ capture and conditioning from the flue gases at the industrial site, and transport to the closest suitable port for further shipment to the Northern Lights storage site located in the Norwegian continental shelf. The transport to the final storage location and the storage itself are not included in the boundaries of the analysis. The industrial sites are considered as early movers. In view of their pioneering effort, only technological solutions currently available are considered for the design of the chains. In addition, the techno-economic framework considers FOAK cost estimates.

The pioneering chains achieved a CO₂ avoidance between 65% (HM Góraźdze) and 87% (SE Skutskär) of the industrial emissions. All pioneering CCUS chains can avoid emissions, while, currently, only KVA Linth and SE Skutskär have the potential for delivering CDR. The 90% capture rate assumed for the capture process is the main contribution to residual emissions. However, additional direct and indirect emissions also occur along the CCUS chain. The direct emissions are related to the combustion of fuel (CO₂ transport is the main responsible), while the indirect emissions are mostly due to the carbon footprint of electricity. The amount of those emissions is affected by factors such as the length of the transport route and the CO₂ intensity of the energy inputs.

The estimated cost of CO₂ avoided of the pioneering chains lies between ca. 100 and ca. 300 EUR/tCO₂. The main driver for this variability is the geographic location, which in turn affects the length and complexity of the transport route and the availability of clean and affordable energy. Scale is another important factor, where larger plants can benefit, to some degree, from economy of scale for certain units (e.g., capture and conditioning) compared to smaller ones. The capture plant is on average the largest cost share, while the contribution of transport is extremely variable depending on the geographical location.

The rollout of the pioneering CCUS chains is characterized by high uncertainty typical of FOAK implementations, which leads to an increased economic penalty. Assuming that several additional CCUS chains will develop in the future, the maturation of CCS technologies and infrastructure will result in opportunities for reducing cost and emissions (from FOAK to NOAK). Still, the current economic penalty must not translate in delayed implementation. Therefore, options should be explored to support the burden of early movers. Targeted policies, e.g., the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, CBAM, and subsidies schemes are critical. A predictable framework to value CDR can also become essential for those chains that can deliver CDR.

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